

Epoxidation of 2 β -Acetoxycholest-5-ene with Cumene Hydroperoxide catalysed by 5,10,15,20-Tetraarylporphyrinatoiron(III) Chlorides

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The reaction of 3 β -acetoxycholest-5-ene (1) with cumene hydroperoxide catalysed by electron-withdrawing and perchlorinated 5,10,15,20-tetraarylporphyrinatoiron(III) chlorides (2a-e) form 3 β -acetoxy-5 α ,6 α -epoxycholestane (3), 3 β -acetoxy-5 β ,6 β -epoxycholestane (4), 3 β -acetoxy-7 α -hydroxycholest-5-ene (5), 3 β -acetoxy-7 β -hydroxycholest-5-ene (6) and 3 β -acetoxy-7-oxocholest-5-ene (7) in different yields depending on the reaction conditions. The higher yields of 5 β ,6 β -epoxides (4) have been obtained with 2,3,7,8,12,13,17,18-octachloro-5,10,15,20-tetraarylporphyrinatoiron(III) chloride (2e) as catalyst than the corresponding 5,10,15,20-tetraarylporphyrinatoiron(III) chlorides (2a-d).

The development of chemical model for cytochrome P450 by reaction of monooxygen donor with iron(III) porphyrin and determination of mechanism of biomimetic oxidation is an important area of current research interest¹⁻³. The reactions of monooxygen donors including iodosylbenzene, hydrogen peroxide, alkyl hydroperoxide and others with iron(III) porphyrins preferably 5,10,15,20-tetraarylporphyrinatoiron(III) chlorides form high valent oxo-iron intermediates which are responsible for biomimetic hydroxylation of hydrocarbons, epoxidation of olefins and oxidation of hetero-atom containing organic substrates¹.

The epoxidation of *cis*-olefins than *trans*-olefins with monooxygen donors catalysed by metalloporphyrins is generally favoured³. Formation of *trans*-epoxidation products from *cis*-olefins and higher *endo*-product from norbornene³⁻⁵ in the above reactions are considered to be radical in nature and may be explained by steric and electronic factors^{5,6}. The epoxidation of 3 β -acetoxycholest-5-ene (1) with iodosylbenzene and other monooxygen donors catalysed by chromium, manganese and iron(III)-5,10,15,20-tetraarylporphyrins⁷ as well as molecular oxygen and 5,10,15,20-tetramesitylrutheniumporphyrin^{8,9} give high degree of β -selectivity. Electronegatively substituted 5,10,15,20-tetraarylporphyrinatoiron(III) chlorides as well as 2,3,7,8,12-13,17,18-octahalogenato-5,10,15,20-tetraarylporphyrinatoiron(III) chlorides (β -X₈TAPFe^{III}Cl) are more robust and efficient catalysts than simple 5,10,15,20-tetraphenylporphyrinatoiron(III) chloride (TPP-Fe^{III}Cl) for hydroxylation of hydrocarbons and epoxidation of olefins^{10,11}. Further, the β , β -alkyl¹² or halogens¹³ substituted porphyrins are distorted to saddle-like conformations and they might show difference in the selectivity than the corresponding metallotetraphenylporphyrins¹⁴. The epoxidation of 3 β -acetoxycholest-5-ene (1) cumene hydroperoxide (CumOOH) catalysed by 5,10,15,20-tetraarylporphyrinatoiron(III) chlorides with halogen substituted aryl groups at the *meso*-positions as well as β , β -positions is reported to enhance the total yields of epoxidation products as well as increase the selectivity in organic solvents.

Results and Discussion

The reaction of 3 β -acetoxycholest-5-ene (1) with CumOOH catalysed by TPPFe^{III}Cl (2a) in dichloromethane gave 3 β -acetoxy-5 α ,6 α -epoxycholestane (3), 3 β -acetoxy-5 β ,6 β -epoxycholestane¹⁵ (4) in 8 and 18% yields respectively, along with other minor products (Table 1). Similarly, the reaction of 1 with cumene hydroperoxide catalysed by 2b and 2c and their reaction products are given in Table 1. The reactions of TAPFe^{III}Cl (2a-e) with CumOOH form TAPFe^{III}-O-OCum which decomposes homolytically¹⁶ in non-polar solvents to C1TAPFe^{IV}=O which are capable of hydroxylating the hydrocarbons but are less effective in the epoxidation of olefins¹⁷. The heterolytic cleavage of C1TAPFe^{III}-O-OCum form the radical cations [C1TAP]^{•+} Fe^{IV}=O which are responsible for high yields of the epoxides. The reaction of C1TAPFe^{III} with CumOOH in presence of NMeIm leads to the formation of radical cation [MeNImTAP]^{•+} Fe^{IV}=O by the push-and-pull mechanism^{18,19}. The radical cation intermediates are able to epoxidise the olefins^{6,19-21}. The stereoselectivity may depend on the structure of olefins as well as metalloporphyrins during rate determination charge transfer complex formation⁶. The structure of iron porphyrins governs the formation of charge transfer complexes which in turn are responsible for higher selectivity of 5 β ,6 β -epoxide from 1 in organic solvents^{7,21}. The use of *N*-methylimidazole (NMeIm) decreases the yield of α , α -epoxide (3), whereas the yield of β , β -epoxide (4) increases (sl. no. 4-6, Table 1). Similarly, the higher yields of 5 β ,6 β -epoxide was obtained when the above reaction was catalysed by 2d. The reaction of 1 with cumene hydroperoxide catalysed by β -Cl₈Cl₈TPPFe^{III}Cl/NMeIm gave higher yield of 4 (sl. no. 10, Table 1) (Scheme 1). The ratio $\beta/(\alpha + \beta) = 0.69$ indicate high β -stereoselectivity which is comparable with the result obtained by epoxidation of 3 β -acetoxycholest-5-ene (1) with TPPFe^{III}Cl-C₆H₅IO⁷ and Me₁₂TPPRu^{IV}(O)₂ systems in organic solvents. The axial hydrogens at C-3 and C-7 positions of 1 prevent the approach of high valent oxo-iron porphyrin radical cations from the α -face leading to high β -selectivity.

tivity. The β -diastereofacial selection is further enhanced by the change of pseudo-*cis*-stereochemistry from the *trans*-stereochemistry at the junction of A and B rings of steroids⁹. Thus the high yield of β,β -epoxide is obtained by epoxidation of 1 with cumene hydroperoxide catalysed by β,β -substituted 5,10,15,20-tetraarylporphyrinatoiron(III) chlorides^{7,21}. Further, the high yield of 7 β -hydroxy (6) may be explained by approach of high valent oxo-iron porphyrins from the β -side to abstract the β -hydrogen and subsequent recombination from the same side²². The formation of 7-oxo compound (7) may be explained by oxidation of

the corresponding hydroxy compounds (5 or 6) with cumene hydroperoxide catalysed by 5,10,15,20-tetraarylporphyrinatoiron(III) chlorides in organic solvents².

The results from above study indicate that higher total yields and β,β -selectivities are obtained in the reactions of 3 β -acetoxycholest-5-ene (1) with CumOOH catalysed efficiently by 2,3,7,8,12,13,17,18-octachloro-5,10,15,20-tetraarylporphyrinatoiron(III) chlorides in absence and presence of *N*-methylimidazole in organic solvents.

Experimental

All m.p.s. were taken on a Thomas Hoover Unimelt capillary apparatus and are uncorrected. Electronic spectra were recorded on a Shimadzu 260 UV spectrophotometer and ¹H nmr spectra on a Perkin-Elmer R-32 (90 MHz) spectrometer. HPLC analysis was carried out on a Shimadzu LC-4a liquid chromatograph using a Zorbax ODS (rps) column (15 $\times$ 4 nm). Acetonitrile at a flow rate of 0.4 ml min⁻¹ was used as the eluent. Detection was done using a Shimadzu SPD-2AS spectrophotometer at 205 nm. Data processing was done using a Shimadzu Chromatopac CR-3A data processor.

All porphyrin synthesis were performed under dry nitrogen atmosphere using distilled and degassed solvents. Pyrrole and mesitaldehyde were distilled before use. 2,6-Dichlorobenzaldehyde, boron trifluoride etherate, *p*-chloranil and cumene hydroperoxide were used as received.

The 5,10,15,20-tetraarylporphyrinatoiron(III) chlorides (2a-e, TAPFe^{III}Cl) including 5,10,15,20-tetraphenylporphyrinatoiron(III) chloride (2a, TPPFe^{III}Cl), 5,10,15,20-tetra(2',4',6'-trimethylphenyl)porphyrinatoiron(III) chloride (2b, Me₁₂TPPFe^{III}Cl) and 5,10,15,20-tetra(2',6'-dichlorophenyl)porphyrinatoiron(III) chloride (2c, Cl₈TPPFe^{III}Cl) were prepared from the corresponding benzaldehyde with pyrrole by modification of literature procedures^{11,23}. 2,3,7,8,12,13,17,18-Octachloro-5,10,15,20-tetraarylporphyrinatoiron(III) chloride (2d, β -Cl₈TPPFe^{III}Cl) was prepared by metallation with FeCl₂·H₂O of the cor-

TABLE I—OXIDATION OF 3 β -ACETOXYCHOLEST-5-ENE (1) WITH CumOOH CATALYSED BY TAPFe^{III}Cl IN DICHLOROMETHANE AT ROOM TEMPERATURE

Sl. no.	System	% Yield of products					β $\alpha + \beta$ for epoxide	β $\alpha + \beta$ for hydroxide
		3	4	5	6	7		
		12.0 ^a	11.3 ^a	9.7 ^a	4.0 ^a	7.5 ^a		
1.	TPPFe ^{III} Cl	8.0	18.2	3.9	4.0	3.7	0.69 ^d	0.51
2.	Me ₁₂ TPPFe ^{III} Cl	12.0	25.0	4.0	3.8	4.8	0.68	0.49
3.	Cl ₈ TPPFe ^{III} Cl	19.3	29.7	2.9	5.1	8.9	0.61	0.64
4.	TPPFe ^{III} Cl/NMI	13.6	23.6	2.3	4.1	4.2	0.63	0.64
5.	Me ₁₂ TPPFe ^{III} Cl/NMI	12.8	31.4	4.7	6.1	7.0	0.71	0.57
6.	Cl ₈ TPPFe ^{III} Cl/NMI	9.2	39.2	3.8	6.8	9.0	0.81	0.64
7.	β -Cl ₈ TPPFe ^{III} Cl	11.2	26.0	3.9	7.2	—	0.70	0.65
8.	β -Cl ₈ TPPFe ^{III} Cl/NMI	9.8	32.0	1.3	2.5	7.3	0.77	0.66
9.	β -Cl ₈ Cl ₈ TPPFe ^{III} Cl	7.3	41.2	2.5	3.9	5.6	0.85	0.61
10.	β -Cl ₈ Cl ₈ TPPFe ^{III} Cl/NMI	7.0	49.3	1.7	3.2	8.0	0.88	0.65

^aHplc retention time.

^dSimilar $\beta/(\alpha + \beta)$ ratios of epoxidation were obtained with C₆H₅IO/TPPFe^{III}Cl and molecular oxygen/Me₁₂TPPRu^{IV} in organic solvents

responding 2,3,7,8,12,13,17,18-octachloro-5,10,15,20-tetra-phenylporphyrins²⁴. 2,3,7,8,12,13,17,18-Octachlorotetra-(2',6'-dichlorophenyl)porphyrinatoiron(III) chloride (2e, β -Cl₈Cl₈TPPFe^{III}Cl) was prepared by bubbling Cl₂ gas to a solution of 2c in *o*-dichlorobenzene at 140° for 1 h²⁵. 3 β -Acetoxy-5 α ,6 α -epoxycholestane⁷ (3), 3 β -acetoxy-5 β ,6 β -epoxycholestane⁷ (4), 3 β -acetoxy-7-oxocholest-5-ene²⁶ (7), 3 β -acetoxy-7 α -hydroxycholest-5-ene²⁷ (5) and 3 β -acetoxy-7 β -hydroxycholest-5-ene²⁷ (6) were prepared by literature procedures.

Oxidation of 3 β -acetoxycholest-5-ene (1) with CumOOH catalysed by perhalogenated porphyrins. General method : To a stirred solution of perhalogenated iron(III) porphyrins (2a-e) (0.20 mmol) in CH₂Cl₂ (10 ml), *N*-methylimidazole (2.0 mmol) was added followed by 3 β -acetoxycholest-5-ene (1; 1.20 mmol) and CumOOH (6.0 mmol) were added in the sequence. The resulting solution was stirred for 3 h and treated with water (25 ml). The organic layer was then separated, dried over anhydrous Na₂SO₄ and the solvent evaporated under reduced pressure. The residue was analysed by tlc and hplc.

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